

Visiting the Margins

INnovative **CUL**tural **ToURisM** in European peripheries

Innovation Factsheet

San Pellegrino in Alpe, Garfagnana

May 2024

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1. Pilot context

The mediaeval village of San Pellegrino in Alpe, historically attested since 1110 A.D. (Trezzini, 2016), today represents the highest permanently inhabited human settlement in the entire Apennine mountain range, with an altitude of 1.525 metres above sea level.

With an average total population that, depending on seasonality, fluctuates between 7 and 11 inhabitants, San Pellegrino in Alpe is also a curious case of administrative management within the Italian legislative panorama. In fact, the hamlet is simultaneously managed by two

municipal administrations (Castiglione di Garfagnana and Frassinoro) located in two different provinces (Lucca and Modena) that are part of two different regions (Tuscany and Emilia-Romagna): the hamlet, therefore, is structured, culturally and politically, as a Tuscan-Emilian island positioned in the middle of the mountain range that divides the two regions (Lemmi & Deri, 2020).

Despite its small size, San Pellegrino in Alpe is home to numerous historical, natural, cultural and religious attractions. Indeed, a vast religious complex is located within the historical centre, which still houses the remains of the Saints - ‘endorsed’ but not officially recognised by the Catholic Church - Pellegrino and Bianco, and also includes the spaces formerly used for resting pilgrims, commonly known as the ‘Hospitale’ (Volpini, 1968; Sommariva, 2011).

Moreover, a section of the same Hospitale now houses the ‘Don Luigi Pellegrini’ Provincial Ethnographic Museum. Opened in 1980 by the parish priest after whom it is named, it is dedicated to the preservation of the memory

The pilot innovations

This report sets out and discusses the innovations that the San Pellegrino pilot case has developed over its three-year term, including those that are still in progress and being completed in the coming months:

- As anticipated, the pilot project aimed to create new tourist itineraries that would allow visitors to discover all the resources of the area. The various cultural, spiritual and natural resources, in fact, were conveyed and linked together to enable a greater understanding of the history and development of the ancient medieval village and its surroundings;
- Designing attractive narratives on the previously mentioned routes in order to engage visitors in local history. These narratives aim to enhance the history of the shrine and pilgrimage routes, as well as the local ethnographic museum;
- Building and implementing the tourism and managerial capacities of local stakeholders, involving them in tourism promotion and development choices through participatory models;
- Engagement and involvement of artists to strengthen communities' attachment to their heritage and share it with others. This course of action was implemented through a play, devised in the early stages of INCULTUM and later performed in the summer seasons of 2022 and 2023, focusing on the history of the place and the creation of the ethnographic museum between the 1960s and 1980s. The play also refers to and mentions the life experiences of historical figures from San Pellegrino in Alpe, taking cues from the museum's objects that, very often, were owned by them;
- Promotional and visitor tools to improve visitors' knowledge of the existence of the village and its tourist offerings. In addition to brochures dedicated to the ethnographic museum and billboards pointing out the data of theatrical performances, several options were developed that involved both the sanctuary - with the creation of a historically themed room - and the museum itself, which was the protagonist of a multi-level digital development.

2. The dual purpose of storytelling: enhancing the tourism offer and strengthening local identity

One of the most important activities organized in San Pellegrino in Alpe involved the creation of a theatrical performance produced in collaboration with the local Ethnographic Museum and written by actress Elisabetta Salvatori. The idea behind the artistic-cultural project is to revitalize the memory of this community and its territory through a narrative approach.

Through the tales and memories of the local inhabitants, the play succeeds in bringing to life a faithful cross-section of rural life that characterised for centuries San Pellegrino in Alpe and

the valley in which it is located - Garfagnana - until the second half of the 20th century.

Through a narrative approach of this kind, it was possible to strengthen the local population's bond with their traditions, while at the same time succeeding in attracting new visitors and also making the museum experience more complete and immersive.

Specifically, the show - entitled 'A priest, two saints, a border and 4000 unique pieces' (*Un prete, due santi, un confine e 4000 pezzi unici*) - tells the story of Don Luigi Pellegrini, parish priest of San Pellegrino in Alpe for almost half a century and the absolute protagonist in the conception and setting up of the ethnographic museum.

Of the various options available, the research team identified Elisabetta Salvatori as the right profile for some fundamental reasons:

- The theme of collective memory, especially of the people living in the peripheral and inland areas of Tuscany, has always been the main element of her playwriting;

- The language she uses is easy to understand, but with great emotional emphasis and very close to the local community and the spirit of popular theatre;
- The actress has an in-depth knowledge of the Garfagnana and San Pellegrino in Alpe territories: elements that have enabled her to describe their specificities in an effective and evocative way.

During the summer of 2022, between July and August, seven performances took place in the courtyard next to the Ethnographic Museum:

- Preview: 3 July
- Repeats: 4 and 31 July, 1, 14, 21 and 28 August

Given the success of the previous season, the show was repeated in 2023, again in San Pellegrino in Alpe but over a longer period of time - between June and September - and inside the religious complex and in the Ethnographic Museum: of the five shows staged last year, one was staged inside the church, while the remaining four in the "Dell'Affresco" hall of the Museum.

- Preview: 25 June
- Repeats: 16 and 30 July, 6 August, 3 September

The theatrical performance was used, among other things, as an instrument to stimulate dialogue and training moments for local actors through the interventions of the administration of the municipality of Castiglione di Garfagnana, the Unione dei Comuni della Garfagnana and the Province of Lucca.

"A priest, two saints, a border and 4,000 unique pieces" has also been reproduced on 13 October 2022 and 6 October 2023 for two exclusive events dedicated - in both cases - to the

students of the second year of Tourism Science at the Campus Foundation.

Elisabetta Salvatori will also perform one last time on the 20th of May 2024 at the final INCULTUM event, organised by the pilot's research team at the “Vittorio Alfieri” theatre in Castelnuovo di Garfagnana. The event will be attended by local, provincial and regional administrations, local high schools and tourism operators.

3. Creating new visitor itineraries

The Garfagnana territory is rich in history, natural resources and is characterised by a strong cultural identity. The creation of new tourist itineraries, in harmony with the values of sustainability and slow tourism, makes it possible to discover wide areas of these territories that are currently outside the traditional tourist routes or constitute destinations of secondary importance.

To achieve this goal, visits have been organized for two consecutive years - on October the 6th 2022 and October 13th 2023 - for university students of Fondazione Campus.

The students of the second year of the Degree Course in Tourism Sciences were invited to participate in an educational visit to San Pellegrino in Alpe supervised by Professor Enrica Lemmi, lecturer in “Tourist itineraries and landscape as cultural heritage” and current Managing Director for Tourism, Education and Research at the Fondazione Campus university, as well as coordinator of the INCULTUM project for the Pilot of the Tuscan-Emilian Apennines.

During the day, they were invited to visit the exhibition dedicated to San Pellegrino inside the Sanctuary of Saints Pellegrino and Bianco, to attend a theatrical performance by local actress Elisabetta Salvatori dedicated to the history of Don Luigi Pellegrini and the Ethnographic Museum, and finally to visit the museum's halls and exhibition.

In fact, at the end of the visit, the students were asked to analyse the site of San Pellegrino in Alpe and the surrounding areas to create innovative tourist itineraries capable of enhancing both the natural aspects of those areas and the historical and cultural ones.

The projects drawn up by the students include a wide range of innovative solutions for rethinking tourism in the Garfagnana area, creating new networks and itineraries between local realities, connecting the resources of places with the local stakeholders.

The students' projects, which included not only the San Pellegrino Site but many other villages and places of interest within their itineraries, were evaluated and helped provide a fresh perspective on the area's tourism potential.

One of the greatest contributions made by the projects was the possibility of extending tourism and activities outside the summer season - indeed, many of the proposals had included the fall and winter seasons.

Hypothesizing possible positive spin-offs from the San Pellegrino in Alpe site's entry into the Tuscan-Emilian Apennine National Park, during the project the research team developed a dialogue with the entity's board of directors to understand the bureaucratic procedures required for the application.

Following a trip to the park authority's headquarters (located in Ligonchio, in the province of Reggio Emilia), three geographical sections have already been hypothesized, from which the most suitable one will be chosen to be included in the proposal. The request for the inclusion of San Pellegrino in Alpe within the park will be submitted officially to the municipality of Castiglione di Garfagnana in the coming months.

The possibility of including the territory of San Pellegrino in Alpe within the Park is a great opportunity with regard to the protection of the area and its tourism potential.

First of all, being part of the Park guarantees greater protection from a landscape and natural point of view and, at the same time, San Pellegrino in Alpe can enjoy greater resonance in the media and beyond.

The Park then acts as a sounding board that can extend knowledge of the site, its history and its tourist attractions to a wider audience.

4. Attractive narratives

San Pellegrino's strategic location has made it a place of passage and crossroads for people, goods, armies and ideas since Roman times. Its historical paths spans more than a millennium, indistinctly and fascinatingly combining founding myths and established facts, united by political, spiritual and commercial aims. One might think that the new millennium has granted a marginal space to an area so distant from the routes of national and international mobility, but on the contrary - and paradoxically thanks to these characteristics - San Pellegrino can once again speak for itself, laying the foundations for a rebirth centred on cultural and sustainable tourism and the local rediscovery of its traditions.

The development of a captivating and fascinating narrative is a fundamental prerequisite for the development of cultural tourism - and consequently also of nature, sustainable and digital tourism - within the San Pellegrino in Alpe site.

The heritage of stories, tales and myths that the village brings with it is of a richness that is hard to find elsewhere in the entire Apennine mountain range.

The enormous religious imprint that hovers over the entire territory also has a peculiarity that makes it unique in the entire western Christian panorama. In fact, despite

the great veneration by Tuscan-Emilian Catholics, the founding saints of the town, Pellegrino and Bianco, are not considered canonical figures within the ecclesiastical institution itself, which 'endures' the popular cult but has never done anything to develop or promote it.

Pellegrino, who according to myth was the heir to the King of Scotland, and his faithful hermit companion Bianco belong perhaps to an older, probably pre-Christian belief, which then developed under the mantle of Christianity to create a continuity centred on the very strength of the site of San Pellegrino: the continuous passage, on the mountaintop, of men, goods, armies, saints and ideas.

The mists of the foundation are certainly attractive, but even the 'official' history of San Pellegrino can provide great events that can faithfully mirror, and exemplify, the power diatribes of the many pre-unitary Italian states.

The historical-mythological heritage of San Pellegrino is a treasure chest that is not afraid to be compared with the narratives of much larger and more famous centres and places, and this is why the valorisation of this intangible asset is fundamental for the subsequent valorisation of the entire area surrounding the village.

The work to develop new narrative models centred on the site of the Pilot has been implemented since the early stages of the INCULTUM Project. Inside the ancient church, in fact, it is now possible to admire a dedicated section in which a number of authentic instruments and effigies have been

installed, as well as information panels describing in great detail the founding myth of San Pellegrino and the subsequent historical journey.

Bringing us closer to modern times, and without disturbing the saints Pellegrino and Bianco, the entire 'Don Luigi Pellegrini' Ethnographic Museum is in essence a great material narrative of rural life that has remained unchanged for centuries: a complex system of values and practices that today can be seen and admired in no less than fourteen rooms on four

floors.

Inside the museum, the INCULTUM Pilot 5 team has also developed a precise enhancement policy, with the conception and implementation of digital devices capable of giving strength, context and memory to the exhibits. Specifically, a number of interactive stations have already been installed - through which it is possible to listen to excerpts of Elisabetta Salvatori's performance - and plates equipped with QR codes that provide visitors with in-depth information and anecdotes on the most peculiar objects and on the historical path that led to the birth of the museum itself.

Two further digitisation actions are still being developed and financed: the first related to the printing of postcards using augmented reality and the second focusing on the installation of holographic 'avatars' that will accompany visitors through the ethnographic exhibition.

Through this project, it has been possible to achieve one of the goals to which all kinds of cultural tourism should aspire, namely the synergy between tradition and innovation, between analog "discovery" and digital deepening.

However, the decision to focus on the intangible heritage of San Pellegrino was not merely a tool for tourism promotion, but also allowed locals and inhabitants of neighboring communities to learn more precisely about their own history and the ways of life that their ancestors preserved until a few decades ago. In tourism practices that recognize themselves in the terms of sustainability and sharing, the relationship with locals is fundamental: it is based precisely on the conscious choice to include local inhabitants and businesses in the chosen path of enhancement and in the choices of doing for future interventions.

A virtuous synergy, made up of simultaneous learning and teaching among all stakeholders, in which knowledge of the history of the area, and its strengths, can only be a prerequisite.

5. Promotional and visitor tools

In the context of promotion and visitor supporting tools, the San Pellegrino pilot case has currently developed and installed illustrative panels inside the Sanctuary. Following a historical study that focused not only on the Sanctuary itself, but also on the lives of the two saints (Bianco and Pellegrino), a large panel was created to illustrate along a timeline the most significant events connected to this place. The installation, inaugurated in the summer of 2021, was attended by a large number of participants, and was accompanied by short guided

tours created by the project collaborators. These panels were created as a visual aid to visitors of the sanctuary and aim to further connect the cultural instances of the village to the existing tourist offer.

Among the primary project objectives of the INCULTUM project, and a key element in the sustainable development of tourism destinations, the INCULTUM research team decided to involve the local community in the planning and development actions of the tourism destination. For this reason, among the first actions planned by the new research group, the team organized training activities with the operators of San Pellegrino in Alpe. Starting in May, two meetings were organized, which were also attended by two local agencies dedicated to tourism promotion of the area and some business owners located in the nearby hamlets of Chiozza, Casone di Profecchia and Col D'Arciana. The two meetings in May 2023 - 15/05 and 29/05 - were designed as training events for the operators, but more importantly as an opportunity to share ideas, opinions and suggestions. The team succeeded in building trusting relationships with locals, subsequently enabling participatory ideas such as the creation of brochures for tourists and their printing, funded by the operators themselves.

The digitalisation project for the San Pellegrino in Alpe museum aims to enhance visitor engagement through immersive storytelling and cutting-edge technology. By integrating modern communication tools, the museum experience will become more dynamic and interactive, particularly for younger audiences who will find a deeper connection with the exhibits, making them feel 'alive' within their context. This approach allows visitors to interact with the museum's content in a personalised way, based on their individual experiences, intentions, and understanding.

Augmented Reality:

The use of Augmented Reality (AR) introduces virtual 3D objects and characters into the real world. At San Pellegrino in Alpe, AR will be implemented through simple paper supports like postcards with QR codes. When scanned with a smartphone, these codes link to digital content that, for instance, displays a virtual human figure welcoming visitors. This method not only allows for flexible content updates but also serves as a memorable souvenir of the innovative visit.

Holograms:

Holograms create three-dimensional images that appear to float in space, enhancing the visitor experience. The museum will use 'holoboxes,' which can be life-sized or smaller, to present

interactive narratives through holographic figures, making the storytelling more engaging and lifelike.

Interactive Audio-Visual Stations:

The museum will feature multimedia stations with audio and video capabilities. The prototype, located in the museum's opening room, includes a small wooden structure housing speakers, a screen, and a tag reader. Visitors can place framed prints depicting museum scenes or historical figures on the structure to trigger 1-2 minute audio-video files related to the theme. This setup enriches the visitor experience by providing contextual multimedia content.

QR Codes:

QR codes will be strategically placed throughout the museum, linking to the museum's website. These codes support two narrative paths: the historical path, detailing the museum's development and its founder, Don Luigi Pellegrini, and the object path, offering descriptions of notable objects. This feature helps visitors, especially those unfamiliar with local culture or young audiences, understand the significance of various exhibits, including large work tools.

Project dissemination

After being developed, the projects were then presented on two different occasions. The first took place during the Assembly of the UNESCO MAB (Man and Biosphere) Reserve of the Tuscan-Emilian Apennines at the Alfieri Theatre of Castelnuovo di Garfagnana on the 15th February 2023.

The second occasion to talk about INCULTUM took place at the Fondazione Campus on the 17th February 2023 during the Winter School organised by the University of Pisa, UNESCO Chair in ICT of Università della Svizzera Italiana

and with the support of Museo della Grafica and of Sistema Museale di Ateneo di Unipi.

Finally, the final INCULTUM event organized by the University of Pisa will be held in May 2024. The event, which will take place at the 'Vittorio Alfieri' Theatre of Castelnuovo di Garfagnana (Province of Lucca) on the morning of the 20th of May, has been conceived as a divulgation and dissemination space for the entire Garfagnana territory and the neighboring Mediavalle del Serchio valley. The coordinators of the project and the researchers involved will talk about the objectives of the INCULTUM project and the results obtained on the San Pellegrino in Alpe pilot. This will be followed by reflections on the possibilities of using

cultural tourism as a tool for the socio-economic revitalisation of peripheral territories and the Garfagnana area in particular. During the conference, which will be attended by students from the 'ISI Garfagnana' high school, local, provincial and regional politicians, local tourism operators and stakeholders involved in the training activities, the theatrical performance 'Un prete, due santi, un confine e 4000 pezzi unici' (A priest, two saints, a border and 4,000 unique pieces), performed by actress Elisabetta Salvatori, will also be staged.

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